

THE THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF SODIUM AND POTASSIUM NITRITES. PART I. STREAMING OF NITROGEN AND CARBON DIOXIDE AND ACTION OF MAGNESIUM OXIDE ON THE FUSED NITRITES

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Experiments have been planned to elucidate the mechanism of the reactions occurring in the decomposition of sodium and potassium nitrites. The primary stage is $2\text{KNO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$; this appears to be followed by the action of the nitrogen peroxide on the potassium oxide as $(\text{K}_2\text{O} + 2\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{KNO}_3 + \text{KNO}_2)$, while nitrogen production appears to result from the action of nitric oxide on the nitrite.

The thermal decomposition of sodium and potassium nitrites has already been studied. Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 177) studied the thermal decomposition of sodium nitrite by heating a small quantity in vacuum in two stages: in the first stage, the heating was slow and cautious and nitric oxide and nitrogen (with traces of nitrogen trioxide) were obtained, while in the second stage the heating was much more intense and a reddish brown gas and oxygen were obtained. The reactions were represented by the following equations:

Ostwald (*Annalen*, 1914, 360, 32) studied the decomposition of alkali nitrites and found that potassium nitrite begins to decompose at 350° according to the following equations:

He studied also the action of nitric oxide and nitrogen peroxide upon the dry nitrites and found that the dry salt was not acted upon by nitric oxide so long as the decomposition itself did not occur and that nitrogen peroxide oxidised potassium nitrite to potassium nitrate. He therefore suggested the following additional reactions:

Oza and Shah (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 9, 56; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 261) studied the thermal decomposition of potassium nitrite alone and in presence of charcoal.

They observed that the proportion of nitric oxide was getting steadily smaller and that of nitrogen steadily greater as the reaction progressed or as the mass of the decomposing nitrite was increased and that in presence of charcoal the reaction became violent and soon went to completion. They explained their results on the following equations :

The reversible nature of the initial stage (i) was a suggestion of great importance. Nitrogen was here shown to be formed only by the action of nitrogen peroxide on the nitrite (ii) and nitric oxide by both the direct decomposition (i) and by the reduction of nitrogen peroxide in contact with the nitrite (iii); this was thus the same as supposed by Ostwald. Fall in the proportion of nitric oxide and increase in that of nitrogen with progress of the reaction were thus ascribed to the intermediate formation of nitrogen peroxide with oxygen from the nitrate (iv).

Reference may also be made to the work of Mehta (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1941, 8, 136), wherein the reactions occurring in the thermal decomposition of nitrites have been summarised as :

He states that the reactions (i), (iii), (iv), (vi) and (vii) are present in the decomposition of potassium nitrite. The work is not yet thoroughly published and it is therefore not possible to judge the strength of evidence leading to the conclusions. It should be observed that equation (i) of Oza and Shah is indicated in this scheme which brings out in addition, two other points of interest; namely: (a) the action of nitrogen peroxide on the metallic oxide (iii), and (b) the production of nitrogen from nitric oxide in contact with the nitrite (vi) and not directly from nitrogen peroxide [(ii) of Oza and Shah]. It will thus be seen that the mode of production of nitrogen requires clearer elucidation.

The present work arose from the observation of Oza and Walawalker (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 315) that pure potassium nitrite melted with decomposition. It was therefore thought that the products of the initial stage in the decomposition might

be swept out by passing a current of some inert gas (nitrogen) on the nitrite in the fused state and the truth or otherwise of the initial stage can thus be established beyond doubt. Further attempts to isolate larger quantities of the products of the initial stage by generating an inert gas (carbon dioxide) in the inside of the decomposition mass, provided results which afforded considerable insight into the mechanism of reactions resulting in the production of nitrogen. The work thus developed interest and it was thought necessary to check the conclusions by carrying out experiments actually with nitric oxide, oxygen and nitrogen peroxide. Further, since the conditions of the above experiments did not allow of a clear observation into the nature of the residue, experiments were undertaken to provide a reliable information in this direction on the heating of the nitrite, in vacuum, on a platinum surface so that glass on which the potassium oxide, present in the residue attacked spoiling the analytical results, was absent. The results of these investigations are described under Parts I and II.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Potassium nitrite used was prepared according to Oza and Walawalker (*loc. cit.*). Sodium nitrite was the recrystallized Merck's extra pure substance which gave the following results on analysis :

0.1536 G. substance gave 0.1300 g. NaCl ; 0.0704 g. substance requires 20.4 c.c. 0.1 N-KMnO₄. Found : Na, 66.64% ; NO₂, 33.27%. Calc. for NaNO₂ : Na, 66.66%, NO₂, 33.33%.

Magnesium carbonate and magnesium oxide were of the extra pure quality of Merck.

Nitrogen was prepared by the action of ammonium chloride solution on sodium nitrite solution. It was bubbled through KOH, alkaline sodium sulphite, acidified ferrous sulphate and ice-cold water and collected over air-free water after letting off about 5 litres. This was then introduced into the evacuated flask (*vide Fig.*) with the aid of a manometer. It was tested for nitric and nitrous oxides which were both found absent.

Analysis of the gaseous products and solid residue was carried out as mentioned by Oza and Shah (*loc. cit.*). The oxide could not be estimated by direct titration and where stated, the figure is calculated from potassium corresponding with the nitrite taken and that corresponding to the nitrite and nitrate present in the residue (found experimentally). Only in experiments with platinum surface (Part II) was the oxide obtained by direct titration with 0.10 *N* succinic acid. The results of analysis of the solid residue are not to be taken as absolute, as the glass wool with which the substance was packed in the heating tube, made accurate analysis impossible. The results are expected to serve the purpose of broad comparison from experiment to experiment or between different experiments.

Apparatus and Procedure.—The apparatus used is shown in the figure. A weighed quantity of the nitrite was kept at S near a padding of glass wool in an electrically heated tube, the ends of which were connected by ground glass joints to a 3-way tap Q on one side and a 4-way tap T on the other. The tap T was connected to the gas reservoir A through the drying tube D. The third way of T was connected to a measuring burette (surrounded by a water condenser C) to measure, over mercury, the volume of gas passed. The fourth way of T was closed during the course of an experiment: when preparing CO₂ or oxygen, a tube containing NaHCO₃ or KClO₃ + MnO₂ was sealed on to this, the whole apparatus evacuated and the gas generated by heating the tube collected in A for use during the experiments.* The tap X led to vacuum pumps through an internal seal and a bulb, K, one-third filled with KOH lye. The empty space, BB, allowed the solution in K to rise when making adjustments and F allowed air to be admitted into the system at the end of any experiment. Volume of gas streamed during an experiment was measured off thus: T was closed to the left and the burette kept open to D. By lowering the levelling tube of the burette and opening the tap T gas was drawn into the burette. T was then closed and the burette read off after adjusting levels of mercury. T was then partially opened to the left and gas allowed to bubble as seen in K. When sufficient gas had passed, T was closed to the left, levels of mercury adjusted and the burette read again. The difference between the readings gave the volume of gas streamed.

Before starting an experiment an accurately weighed quantity (1 g.) of the nitrite was introduced at S between plugs of glass wool. All the ground glass joints were fitted up with vacuum grease and the system evacuated and allowed to stand for one day to test for leakage, if any. After adjusting the temperature of the furnace, measured by a mercury-in-silica thermometer (850°) the desired gas was streamed at a practically uniform rate such that about 60 c.c. were passed in about 15 minutes. All experiments were conducted at and near (50° higher) the melting point of the nitrite. The rate of decomposition at these temperatures is negligibly small (Oza and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

Preliminary experiments were carried out with carbon dioxide as streaming gas. The volume streamed was not measured and the experiments were carried out mainly to test the formation of nitrate (diphenylamine test) and oxide in the residue and of nitrate, if any, in the alkali bulb, K. Quite a number of experiments were done and in all, with-

* In actual practice the gas first filled in A was drawn out by working the hyvac pump. A fresh lot prepared on a second heating was collected for use in the experiments.

out exception, the residue was found to contain oxide and nitrate while the alkali never contained any nitrate. The gaseous products, on the other hand, always contained at least a trace of nitric oxide thus explaining why no nitrate was ever present in the alkali.

The results of experiments with nitrogen as streaming gas are given in Table I. The results showed that (i) N_2O_3 alone and no NO or nitrogen was produced in experiments with $NaNO_2$ though all the three gases were produced with KNO_2 ; (ii) the solid residue of $NaNO_2$ did not contain nitrate though it contained oxide; (iii) in the case of KNO_2 , where both NO and nitrogen were present in gas, production of nitrate also occurred in the residue. It thus appeared that nitrogen production was related to nitrate production (*vide* equations of Ray).

TABLE I

Nitrogen as streaming gas on fused nitrites (1 g.)

Substance.	Temp.	Total gas passed.	Total gas obtained.	Composition of the gas			Compn. of residue		
				N_2O_3 .	NO.	N_2 .	NO_3 (Na or K)	NO_2 (Na or K)	O. (Na or K)
$NaNO_2$	330°	53.84 c.c.	56.13 c.c.	2.29	Trace	Trace	0.0	0.9884	0.0052
"	380	60.1	62.65	2.49	"	"	0.0	0.9866	0.0061
KNO_2	410	..	65.62	2.63	0.59	"	0.00825	0.9682	0.0138
"	460	54.68	61.62	4.73	0.84	0.37	0.0150	0.9470	0.0224

These experiments thus yielded a positive undeniable proof of the initial stage in the decomposition of the nitrites, *viz.*,

where M is the alkali metal atom. They also showed that the nitrate production was in some way connected with the formation of nitric oxide or nitrogen or both.

The results of experiments with CO_2 as streaming gas are given in Table II and show that (i) nitric oxide, nitrogen and nitrate are all produced with both the nitrites at all temperatures; (ii) the production of oxides of nitrogen is greater with $NaNO_2$ than with KNO_2 and yet the production of nitrogen and of nitrate is uniform in comparable experiments.

TABLE II

Carbon dioxide as streaming gas on fused nitrites (1 g.)

Substance.	Temp.	Total gas passed (N.T.P.)	Total gas obtained (N.T.P.)	Composition of the gas			Compn. of residue	
				N_2O_3 .	NO	N_2 .	NO_3 (Na or K)	NO_2 (Na or K)
$NaNO_2$	330°	54.38 c.c.	6.06 c.c.	3.4	2.2	0.46	0.0077	0.977
"	380	55.71	13.32	7.0	5.66	0.66	0.0175	0.947
KNO_2	410	54.71	4.0	2.5	1.0	0.50	0.0085	0.9625
"	460	54.88	5.7	3.8	1.2	0.70	0.0185	0.9492

These experiments indicated the production of nitric oxide and nitrogen even with NaNO_2 at 330° and 380° where in the corresponding experiments with nitrogen (Table I) no nitric oxide and nitrogen are met with. This may be ascribed to the greater effective concentration of the oxides of nitrogen in these experiments than in the others brought about by the displacement of N_2O_5 from the nitrites by CO_2 as :

It is seen in the above experiments that the production of nitrate is in some way connected with the production and reduction of oxides of nitrogen. This might occur in any of the ways pointed out in the introduction. Since the production of oxides of nitrogen is but small in all these experiments it was thought that a more correct idea of the operating factors can be had if the oxides of nitrogen could be released in larger amounts. With this end in view it was thought of generating CO_2 within the decomposing mass of the nitrites by admixing the nitrites with some readily decomposable carbonate. An intimate mixture of 0.25 g. nitrite and excess of magnesium carbonate was prepared and put into the heating tube S of the apparatus and the end of the tube projecting out of the furnace (on the side of T) was sealed off. Since MgCO_3 decomposed more quickly than at 350° temperature of the furnace was adjusted to that of the experiment as quickly as possible. The results of these experiments are given in Table III. They show that

TABLE III

Heating a mixture of magnesium carbonate and 0.25 g. nitrites

Substances.	Temp.	Total gas evolved (N.T.P.).	Composition of gas			Composition of residue		
			N_2O_5 .	NO.	N_2	NO_3 . (Na or K)	NO_2 . (Na or K)	O. (Na or K)
NaNO_2	380°	33.22 c.c.	2.4	29.24	0.58	0.0383	0.1025	0.0487
KNO_2	380	19.25	2.4	17.02	0.33	0.0220	0.133	0.0478
"	410	22.34	2.8	19.21	0.33	0.0231	0.1222	0.0541
"	460	17.65	2.3	14.56	0.70	0.02385	0.1355	0.0451

(i) nitric oxide and nitrogen peroxide are always present in the gas and the amount of nitrogen trioxide is practically the same in all the experiments ; not only so, it is always smaller than those in experiments of Tables I and II ; (ii) the amounts of nitric oxide are far greater than those of nitrogen, the amounts of the latter being negligibly small even at 460° ; (iii) the residue (soluble portion) contains both oxide and nitrate together with a practically constant amount of unchanged nitrite.

The results showed without a shadow of doubt that nitrogen was not the primary product of decomposition of the nitrites and that nitrogen production was not directly connected to nitrate production (equations of Ray, *loc. cit.*). The fact that the amounts of N_2O_5 in all these experiments are similar, receives explanation on its steady escape in small amounts during the progress of the reactions. Again the facts that (i) the amounts of N_2O_5 in these experiments are much less than what would be expected under the prevailing conditions and (ii) the free gas consists of almost all nitric oxide, show that nitrogen

peroxide, produced in the initial stage, is either all used up (fixed up in some way) or reduced to nitric oxide—that this component of the products of the initial stage is more readily reactive than the other. Further, the uniform nature of the gaseous products and of the residues in all these experiments suggests lack of complications in the reactions. The above facts together with the fact that magnesium oxide is present in excess in the residues would suggest that nitrogen peroxide reacts at the instant of its liberation with the magnesium oxide present to form nitrite and nitrate and the former being unstable under the prevailing conditions (Ray, *loc. cit.*) passes into nitrate and nitric oxide forming, at the same time, a little nitrogen (Ray, *loc. cit.*).

These experiments thus suggest that nitrogen peroxide reacts at the instant of its liberation with magnesium oxide present in the residue. In the decomposition of pure nitrites (*i.e.* in absence of magnesium oxide) the product of the decomposition contains alkali oxide—a substance much more reactive to nitrogen peroxide than magnesium oxide. The results therefore lend support to the view (*vide* introduction) that the alkali oxide in the residue reacts with the nitrogen peroxide of the products of the initial stage. This view is corroborated by the results, given in Table IV on heating an intimate mixture of nitrite and magnesium oxide which show (i) still smaller production of N_2O_3 than in

TABLE IV

Heating a mixture of magnesium oxide and 0.25 g. of nitrite

Substance.	Temp.	Total gas evolved (N.T.P.).	Composition of gas			Composition of residue		
			N_2O_3 .	NO.	N_2 .	KNO_3 .	KNO_2 .	K_2O .
KNO_2	460	27.29 c.c.	1.58	24.87	0.84	0.01305	0.119	0.0645
„	500	23.19	0.94	21.34	0.91	0.02415	0.153	0.0525

the preceding set of results and (ii) the same negligibly small production of nitrogen even when the temperature is raised to 500°.

It is interesting to observe in all the experiments of Tables III and IV that (i) nitrogen is present in negligible amounts and (ii) nitrite is present in the residues in fairly appreciable amounts and still the reaction, which is very vigorous at the start, becomes considerably slackened in the course of about fifteen minutes though a large excess of magnesium oxide is always present. The latter point could be explained if it is supposed that the nitrite becomes coated with a layer of magnesium nitrate and decomposition of the enclosed nitrite is thus prevented. Such a course would prevent access of nitric oxide to nitrite suggesting that lack of nitrogen production may be due to this cause. In other words, nitrogen production might be occurring by reduction of nitric oxide in contact with the nitrite. Since surface of the nitrite is not exposed to the attack of nitric oxide (it is enclosed by a coating of magnesium nitrate) no nitrogen results. Although there is plenty of nitric oxide in the gas it is in contact with the nitrate and not with the nitrite.

CONCLUSION

The above experiments enable us to draw certain inferences as to the mechanism of reactions occurring in the thermal decomposition of sodium and potassium nitrites. The initial stage in the decomposition is undoubtedly

the oxides of nitrogen, and not nitrogen itself, being the product of the initial stage.

The nitrogen peroxide and the alkali oxide produced in (i) are likely to react with each other in which case nitrite and nitrate would result as

Equation (ii) shows the production of nitrate and disappearance of nitrogen peroxide as found in practice. Equations (i) and (ii) together show also why the residue contains free alkali.

The above study does not enable a definite explanation to be given of the reactions producing nitrogen but makes it likely that it may be the result of the action of nitric oxide on the nitrite. Experiments have been performed to throw light on this point and will be described in Part II.

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